

Tsaritsa Jelena of Serbia as an Independent Patron of Arts between 1355 and 1366

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Abstract: This essay discusses the acts of patronage by Jelena (Jelisaveta), *Tsaritsa* of Serbia, undertaken after the death of her husband, Tsar Stefan Dušan. It investigates how they contributed to the reconciliation of the Serbian and Byzantine churches and to the establishment of Jelena's image as an independent governor. By using the politics of memory, the *Tsaritsa* attempted to represent her deceased husband as a pious ruler, in order to ground her own power and that of her son on the shared Serbian-Byzantine memory of patronage. When establishing the cult of Patriarch Kallistos in the Serbian milieu, Jelena shifted the emphasis from ecclesiastic conflict to political negotiations.

Keywords: Jelena of Serbia, Tsar Stefan Dušan, reconciliation of churches, patronage, Athos, Serres, ideology

This essay² is going to discuss the role of Serbian *Tsaritsa* Jelena (Jelisaveta) as an independent patron of arts after the death in 1355 of her

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husband, King/Tsar³ Stefan Dušan.⁴ By analyzing the monuments that are associated with or can be attributed to the Tsaritsa's sponsorship, I will show how the nature of her commissions reflected the main political trends of her rule and enabled her to establish her own royal ideology.

Tsaritsa Jelena (1315-1374), niece of Bulgarian Tsar Ivan Alexander and wife of Serbian King (Tsar) Stefan Dušan,⁵ is well-known in Serbian, Bulgarian, and international historiography, due to her active participation in the political life of the medieval Balkans and her exceptional visit to Mount Athos, typically banned for women.⁶ Some authors⁷ also have discussed Jelena's patronage role over such foundations as St Sabbas' cell in Karyes and Matejče Monastery.

However, to understand the nature of Jelena's artistic policies one needs to view them within the political climate of the period and to assess them against the status of the Serbian Empire and its rulers in the region. Already Novaković and Ostrogorsky⁸ noted that Jelena went to Serres after the death of her husband, and ruled there independently relying on *Kesar* Vojihna, Gouverneur of Drama, and Uglješa Mrnjavčević, holding the title of *despot* and being the "major" of the town. Byzantine historian John Kantakouzenos characterized Jelena's governance style in the following way: during the tensions between Stefan Dušan's brother Simeon and the Tsar's son Uroš, "Jelena, his mother, being equally distrustful to the son and to Simeon, the brother of her husband, subjected many towns and surrounded herself with significant forces, held the power for herself, not fighting with anybody nor raising to war with anybody."⁹ However, already by May of 1356, Jelena took the monastic veil, as Stefan Uroš's charter to Hilandar monastery¹⁰ mentions her s Jelisaveta, i.e., under her monastic name.¹¹ It is worth noticing that scribe Gabriel, who made a Pentecostarion for

3 On the complexity of the 'tsar' title among the Balkan Slavs and its correlation with the Byzantine "basileus," see: Ostrogorski 1935; Bakalov 1995; Maksimović 1998.

4 Soulis 1984: 91-92; Mihaljičić 1989: 26-28, 66-70.

5 Purković 1975.

6 Konidarēs 2003.

7 Grujić 1935; Soulis 1954, 130; Živojinović 1982; Dimitrova 2002: 262-271; Belyakova (Leber) 2015; Smolčić-Makuljević 2016: 184-186.

8 Novaković 1960: 164-170; Ostrogorski 1965: 3-5, 91, 104-105, 113-114.

9 Kantakouzenos 1832: Vol. III, 314.

10 Novaković 1912: 308-310.

11 Radić, Milutinović 1994 suggest that the taking of vows happened on Easter 24th of April, 1356.

St. Catherine's Monastery on Mount Sinai on behalf of Metropolitan Jacob of Serres, included the *Tsaritsa* under her monastic name in the ruler-dating formula, and used an expression in plural, the "ruling tsars", when referring to "nun" Jelisaveta and her son Uroš.¹² Thus, one may conclude that the Serbian Church elite recognized Jelena as a ruler despite her monastic status.

As a first act of independent patronage, Jelena commissioned the murals at Matejče monastery, recently dated to 1348-1352.¹³ The church was destined for the *Tsaritsa's* burial place and, therefore, she and her son are depicted as founders, whereas Stefan Dušan is portrayed as the sanctioning authority and as a church sponsor.¹⁴ However, among the historical figures included in the murals, one may find also Patriarch Joanikije, belonging to the *ktetoric* composition, and the monastery's *hegoumenos* Makarije, whose portrait is situated on the northern part of the eastern wall¹⁵. The presence of the two clerics in close association with the founders' images may suggest that they were appointed as the enterprise's managers, who oversaw the construction and decoration on behalf of the royal founders.¹⁶ Consequently, even before the death of her husband Jelena stayed in close connection with the ecclesiastic hierarchs¹⁷, who were later inclined to recognize her ruling status despite of the monastic veil.

Another argument of Jelena's reliance on the church structure for political support is her benefactions to the Athonite foundations. In addition to her widely discussed visits to Athos and patronage over St Sabbas' cell at Karyes,¹⁸ her later ties with the Holy Mount Athos were strengthened through an extraordinary rich donation to the Lavra of

12 *Stojanović* 1902: Vol. I, p. 42, no. 116: Въ лѣто бѣжѣи индиктион г царствующимъ въ насъ благочестивымъ царемъ Стефаномъ Оурошомъ и матери его монахи Елисаветѣ. - "in the year 6868, indiction 13th, when the pious tsars, Stefan Uroš and his mother nun Jelisaveta, were ruling over us".

13 *Dimitrova* 2002: 266-271. However, according to Patriarch Pajsije (r. 1614-1647), the monastery had not been finished by the time of Stefan Dušan's death (1355), so Jelena and Uroš completed the edifice and adorned it (*Patrijarh Pajsije* 1993: 92).

14 *Dimitrova* 2002: 185-187; *Korunovski, Dimitrova* 2006: 34.

15 *Dimitrova* 2002: 187-190.

16 *Belyakova (Leber)* 2019: 4-6, 11-13.

17 As later historical cases prove, Church dignitaries often undertake care of monasteries and other ecclesiastic institutions independently, in cases of a weak or nonexistent (Orthodox) state authority, see: *Matić* 2018.

18 *Grujić* 1935; *Belyakova (Leber)* 2015; *Smolčić-Makuljević* 2016. On Jelena's visit and its connection with abaton, see: *Soulis* 1954: 10; *Živojinović* 1982: 123.

Fig. 1. The Church of Dormition, Matejče monastery, 1350s. The donor composition with Jelena and Uroš and the figure of Stefan Dušan, south wall. Photo by A. Adashinskaya

St Athanasios. According to the *chrysobull* given by Stefan Dušan's son, Tsar Stefan Uroš, to Lavra monastery in 1361,¹⁹ the Athonite foundation received the Monastery of All Saints with its possessions as a *metochion*. The donation, as the charter reads, had several peculiarities: the endowment was very generous and substantial; it was not the ruler, but rather his "mother," who initiated the donation; and the gift had a commemorative character "honoring and [providing for] the soul salvation of the three-times blessed and commemorated emperor (tsar)" Stefan Dušan²⁰. Considered altogether, these three

19 *Actes de Lavra*: Vol. III, 82-85, no. 140; *Solovjev, Mošin* 1936: 200-207 no. XXVIII; *Živojinović* 2006: 87.

20 The charter is preserved in two versions, in Greek and Old Church Slavonic, issued by the same chancellery of Tsar Stefan Uroš. Probably, the Greek text was produced first, whereas the Slavonic one – a month later, *Actes de Lavra*: Vol. III, 83. Greek: ἐποίησαν δὲ (καὶ) ἐπιμέλειαν ὑπὲρ τῆς τιμῆς (καὶ) τῆς ψυχικῆς σ(ωτη)ρί(ας) τοῦ τρισμακαριστοῦ (καὶ) ἀοιδίμου βασιλ(έως)

factors suggest a quite straightforward political picture of the period.

According to Danilo's continuer,²¹ Constantinopolitan Patriarch Kallistos "sends to excommunicate the Tsar with the [Serbian] Patriarch and his archpriests. When this happened, the Tsar comes to repent and looks for resolving this enmity, but he cannot do so because of the title and [conquered] towns. And, after this, he ends this life and gets buried, leaving this enmity unburied behind." Having rather a political than actual religious reasoning, such as the conquest of Greek Territories, the proclamation of Stefan Dušan as the Tsar of the Serbs and Greeks, and the establishment of the Serbian Patriarchy,²² this event caused, nevertheless, a reputational harm and practical diplomatic difficulties to the Serbian state. Thus, many political actions undertaken by Stefan Dušan's heirs in different parts of the fragmented empire should be considered as attempts to settle the "unburied enmity" with Constantinople.²³ However, the present donation act witnessed that the relations with other institutions representing the Greek Orthodox Church were settled much earlier than those with the Patriarchate of Constantinople.

Thus, the introductory part of the donation set forth the conditions attached by the Serbian ruler to the gift:²⁴

- To care about the salvation of the soul of "the three-times blessed and commemorated emperor (tsar);"
- To write down his name into the *Synodikon* in order to acclaim and bless him together with [other] holy emperors according to church practice;
- To write down his name in their holy church *brebion* in order to commemorate him on those days together with the glorious emperors and *ktetors*;
- To perform the commemoration of the memory of his soul on the day of the dormition of his soul.

τοῦ αὐθ(έν)του - *Actes de Lavra*: Vol. III, 84; Slavonic: сътворише же и прилежание в чьсти и д(оу)шевнѣмъ сп(а)сени трѣбл(а)жен'наго и пр(и)снопоминаемаго цара - *Solovjev, Mošin* 1936: 203, no. XXVIII.

21 *Daničić* 1886: 381.

22 *Mošin* 1946; *Bogdanović* 1975; *Petrović* 1979; *Barišić* 1982.

23 Besides *Tsaritsa* Jelena's policies regarded here, one should also consider the Act by Jovan Uglješa of 1368 and Knez Lazar's embassy of 1375 - *Petrović* 1979; *Barišić* 1982.

24 *Solovjev, Mošin* 1936: 202, no. XXVIII.

Moreover, the gift itself is called “repayment\reward for such great kindness,” implying the establishment of exchange relations between the donor and the monastery, whereas *Tsaritsa Jelena* (“my Lady Empress/Tsaritsa and mother”)²⁵ is singled out as the initiator of the endowment act, asking her son to provide for the chrysobull confirming her donations. Consequently, one may safely assume that the gift to the Lavra was undertaken by Jelena before 1361 for the commemoration and veneration of her deceased husband. Moreover, this commemoration had to be performed in two forms, privately and politically. The Great Lavra monks commemorated the Serbian Tsar as a private person, through the performance of memorial services and the mentioning of his name during the *proskomidia* rite, together with other *ktetors*, according to the indications of the *brebion*. They also remembered him as a political figure distinguished by his contribution to the Orthodoxy, as the entry of Stefan Dušan’s name into the *Synodikon* may be interpreted only in this way. This unusual occurrence of the excommunicated ruler among the emperors glorified for their orthodoxy meant that the Lavriotes pronounced the acclamations to Stefan Dušan during the solemn service on the day of the Triumph of Orthodoxy together with “other holy emperors.”²⁶

This way, the condition of the private and political veneration, i.e., the recognition of Stefan Dušan’s legitimacy despite of his Constantinopolitan excommunication, was initiated by *Tsaritsa Jelena* and agreed to by the monks of the Athonite Lavra. One may suggest that the political influence of the Serbian Empire in the province of Macedonia,²⁷ as well as the obvious economic reasons (extreme generosity of the donation)

25 ἀμειβομένη τὴν τοιαύτην αὐτ(ῶν) καλογνωμί(αν) ἢ κερὰ μου ἢ δέσποινα ἢ μάννα μου ἔδωκε - *Actes de Lavra*: Vol. III, 84; и взданиє творе такового тѣхъ добронравііа г(о)с(по)жда ми ц(а)р(и)ца м(а)ти ц(а)р(с)тва ми - *Solovjev, Mošin* 1936: 202, no. XXVIII.

26 ἔγραψαν τὸ ὄνομα αὐτοῦ ἐν τῷ συνοδικῷ ὥστε εὐφημεῖσθαι (καὶ) μακαρίζεσθαι αὐτ(όν) μετὰ τῶν εὐσεβ(ῶν) βασιλέ(ων) κατὰ τὴν τῆς ἐκκλησί(ας) συνήθειαν - *Actes de Lavra*: Vol. III, 84; и написалъ име юго въ синодицѣ іако же благохвалити и бл(а)жити юго съ бл(а)гочъстивіими ц(а)ри по цр(ѣ)ковному вбичаю - *Solovjev, Mošin* 1936: 203, no. XXVIII. Translation: “They inscribed his name in the *Synodikon* in order to praise and acclaim him together with holy emperors in accordance with the church rite.” For more details, see: *Rigo* 2017: 271; *Adashinskaya* 2020: 593-594.

27 Macedonia, as a province of the Palaiologan era, doesn’t completely correspond to the modern geographic region. Here, Macedonia designates the region between the rivers Strymon and Maritza, as it was usually applied by Byzantine writers starting with the 12th century (*Koder* 2000: 20-21, 24), that included the cities of Thessaloniki and Serres. During the last decades of Stefan Dušan’s reign, the Serbs occupied a significant part of the province with the exception of the city of Thessaloniki; the border between the Byzantine and Serbian lands seems to pass on the river Mesta/Nestos – *Soullis* 1984: 93.

Fig. 2. St. Kallistos Chapel, Sts. Theodores cathedral, Serres, after 1363.
Photo by A. Adashinskaya

motivated the monastery to undertake this step, breaking up with the main political line of the Patriarchate of Constantinople. Indeed, the gift had an unusually large size and consisted of a *metochion*, adjusted lands (all situated in the area north of Serres), and a monetary income from taxes.²⁸

Another act of patronage performed by Jelena, the chapel adjoined to the cathedral of Sts. Theodoroi at Serres, should be also viewed in the

²⁸ Ćirković 1956: 145.

context of her memory politics. Both the establishment of the deceased Tsar's commemorations and the canonization of the Constantinopolitan Patriarch by the Serbian Church (discussed further) served as attempts to settle the conflict with the Patriarchate of Constantinople. In this sense, the historical memories of the past clashed and its actors had to be replaced with a more positive image of the Serbian-Byzantine ecclesiastic relations, as the concepts of Past legitimize and frame the conflicts/reconciliations, identities, or social orders of the Present,²⁹ and in its Present the fragmented Serbian state needed an ally in its struggles with the approaching Ottomans. Consequently, the memory of the Serbian excommunication caused by Stefan Dušan's decision to establish the local patriarchate and empire in 1346 should have been replaced by the acts of piety aimed at reconciliation and peace-making. Thus, after the negotiation of Stefan Dušan's orthodoxy and righteousness with the monasteries of Mount Athos, Jelena made an effort to represent the ideological unity of the Serbian and Greek Churches through the commencement of the cult of Patriarch of Constantinople Kallistos, who had previously excommunicated the Serbian Church and died during his visit to Jelena's court.

The cult of Patriarch Kallistos as a saint is attested scarcely,³⁰ though there are some reasons to suggest that it originated around the time of his death. As John Kantakouzenos reports, Patriarch Kallistos was sent by John V as head of an embassy to the widowed Jelena. The embassy negotiated the joint actions "to attack the barbarians in Thrace, who made evil to the countries of the Romans and the Triballs and plundered for many days... The spouse of the king accepted the embassy with great honor..."³¹ However, the embassy's negotiations did not achieve tangible results, because the patriarch died in the summer of his arrival (1363 or 1364)³² to Serres, during a plague epidemic: "It happened, that the patriarch himself was fallen down by the heavy decease which, finally, caused the death to him and, after a short while, to his companions."³³

29 Connerton 1989; Nora 1989; Wang 2018: 27-39.

30 Gedeon 1899: 116.

31 τοῖς ἐν Θράκῃ βαρβάροις ἐπιθέσθαι, κακῶς καὶ τὴν Ῥωμαίων καὶ Τριβαλλῶν ποιούσι καὶ ληϊζομένοις ὁσημέρα... ἡ μὲν οὖν Κράλη γαμετὴ τὴν πρεσβείαν ἐδέξατο προθύμως... - *Kantakouzenos* 1832: Vol. III, p. 361.

32 *Novaković* 1960: 123-124, 140-150; *PLP*, no. 10478; *Dölger* 1965: Vol. V, no. 3095 considered that Kallistos died in 1363; *Ostrogorski* 1965: 129, 133 and *Soulis* 1984: 90 – preferred 1364 as the year of Kallistos' death. See also *Mošin* 1949 for the circumstances of the embassy.

33 οὗτω δὲ συμβάν, αὐτὸς τε ὁ πατριάρχης ἐνεπεπτώκει νόσω χαλεπῇ, ὑφ' ἧς καὶ ἐτελεύτησε, καὶ οἱ ἄλλοι οἱ συνόντες, πλὴν ὀλίγων... - *Kantakouzenos* 1832: Vol. III, p. 362

The mission of Kallistos to Serres is also mentioned briefly by a number of short chronicles. The Chronicles of Dionysiou Monastery (Dionysiou Ms. 219) and those in the codex Biblioteca Marciana Ms. Gr. 408 (coll. 672) notice that in the year 6872 [1363-1364] Patriarch Kallistos was sent with an embassy to Serbia and died there, whereas the Chronicle in the codex of Bologna (Biblioteca Universitaria, Ms. Gr. 3632) dates his death with July 20, 1363.³⁴

The patriarch's sudden death made the Serbian *Tsaritsa* to take care about the funerals of the great hierarch: "Elisabeth buried the deceased patriarch with great honor in the Metropolis of Feres (Serres)³⁵ and venerated him in a great measure."³⁶ However, not only the mission of the alive Constantinopolitan patriarch, but also the presence of Kallistos' body in Serres appeared to be an event of great importance. Thus, according to John Kantakouzenos, Jelena started to venerate the deceased as her "intercessor":

"When from the monasteries of Mount Athos, and, especially, from the Holy Lavra, the most pious and the most worthy of praise ones arrived to her and asked to arrange the transfer of the body of the patriarch to Athos and to bury him at their place, she did not give it, saying that she herself has a need in his intercession (προστασία) and (he) should be left with her."³⁷

Thus, Jelena intended to keep Kallistos' body as relics, whose presence would symbolize the ecclesiastic unity of Serbia and Byzantium. This mission of the Constantinopolitan patriarch is usually regarded as the first attempt to establish relations between the Serbian and Byzantine Churches after the excommunication of 1346.³⁸ However, its immediate

34 Schreiner 1975: Vol. 1, 66 (No. 7.16), 93 (No. 9.16).

35 Except for one case (*Kantakouzenos*: Vol. I, p. 251), Kantakouzenos always refers to the city of Serres under the name of "Pherai" (62 instances according to the TLG), see: *Fatouros, Krischer* 1982, Vol. 1, p. 295, footnote 365. The use of this name is considered an attempt to archaize the narrative, *Jireček* 1911: Vol. 1, p. 382, footnote 32.

36 ἀποθανόντα δὲ τὸν πατριάρχην ἔθαψέ τε μεγαλοπρεπῶς ἡ Ἐλισάβετ ἐν τῇ μητροπόλει Φερῶν καὶ ἐτίμησε διαφερόντως *Kantakouzenos* 1832: Vol. III, p. 362.

37 ἀφικομένων δὲ παρ' αὐτὴν καὶ ἐκ τῶν ἐν Ἄθῳ φροντιστηρίων τῶν σπουδαιότερων καὶ ἀντιποικιμένων ἀρετῆς, μάλιστα δὲ Λαύρας τῆς ἱερᾶς, καὶ δεηθέντων ἐφείναι τὸν πατριάρχου νεκρὸν ἐν Ἄθῳ μεταγαγεῖν καὶ θάψαι παρὰ σφίσι, οὐκ ἐνέδωκεν, αὐτὴ μάλιστα εἰπούσα δεῖσθαι τῆς ἐκείνου προστασίας, καὶ δεῖν εἶναι κατέχειν παρ' ἑαυτῆ. - *Kantakouzenos* 1832: Vol. III, p. 362.

38 *Bogdanović* 1975: 81-86; *Petrović* 1979: 29-31, 49; *Purković* 1976: 5-7.

Fig. 3. St. Kallistos Chapel, Sts. Theodores cathedral, Serres. The interior decoration, after 1363. Photo by A. Adashinskaya

practical reason was a military threat to the Byzantine Empire caused by the Ottoman presence in Gallipoli,³⁹ whereas the ecclesiastic reconciliation seems to be a 'reward' promised to the Serbs. John V himself chose Kallistos for the embassy, and this choice indicates that the mission had two main goals: to make an alliance against the Turks and to establish a certain agreement concerning the excommunication. Against this background, Jelena's attempt to establish the cult of the recently deceased Constantinopolitan patriarch on the Serbian territory with the assistance of the Serbian Church might be justified politically as a step toward the legitimization of the Serbian Patriarchate. In doing so, Jelena acted not as a royal widow, but rather as a ruler who, by using the tools of patronage, tried to reach a series of political goals.

There is a possibility that the chapel adjusted to the cathedral of Hagioi Teodoroi in Serres was made for the occasion of Kallistos' death with consideration to the future cult developments. Nowadays dedicated to Patriarch Kallistos, this small structure contains an arcosolium inbuilt into the northern wall, and a recently-discovered medieval burial with

³⁹ Nicol 1993: 262-265.

a marble coffin.⁴⁰ Its medieval fresco-decoration comprises the *Deesis* in the conch of the apse, having an obviously funerary character.⁴¹ This burial space was assigned to an important deceased individual, and taking into consideration Jelena's efforts to venerate Patriarch Kallistos in Serres, the late-medieval character of the chapel, and its present dedication to St Patriarch Kallistos, it seems possible that this edifice was the commission of Jelena to contain Kallistos' tomb.

Her acts of private devotion are more obvious from the commission of manuscripts. Between 1355-1363, at Jelena's order, an anonymous scribe from Mount Athos prepared three⁴² manuscripts that are nowadays kept in the National Library of Athens: *EBE* 2004 (Ms. Suppl., 4) Synaxarion for March – April, *EBE* 2049 (Ms. Suppl. 35) Menaion for April, and *EBE* 2035 (Ms. Suppl. 49) Menaion for February.⁴³ According to the scribe's notes, the codices were ordered through the mediation of a certain Dorotej, who can be identified with the *hegoumenos* of Hilandar and the *protos* of the Holy Mount acting in the 1350s-1360s.⁴⁴ Linos Politis had doubts about the destination of the books, proposing that they could be made for Jelena's private library;⁴⁵ however, taking into consideration their ecclesiastic service content, it is more probable that the order was made by the *Tsaritsa* on behalf of the Prodromos Monastery near Serres.⁴⁶

Even in this private donation, one can see the image of the Serbian female ruler and not that of a widow or even a nun, whom she became immediately after her husband's death. At least, such was the official representation projected to Jelena's / Jelisaveta's subjects. Several times, the scribe's remarks appealed to the *Tsaritsa* directly, by using a strange combination of her laic title (*augusta, despoina*) and her monastic name:

40 *Samsarēs* 2016: 67-68.

41 On the commemorative character of the *Deesis* iconography: *Velmans* 1980-1981; *Thierry* 1974; see further bibliography in *Walter* 1980.

42 In the colophon, the scribe notes that these were not the only books he produced for the *Tsaritsa*, as he has already completed six menaia and intended to make further three for the Athonite Lavra - *Politis* 1991: 72; *Belyakova (Leber)* 2019: 22.

43 *Politis* 1930; *Politis* 1991: 72-74, 96; *Belyakova (Leber)* 2019: 21-23.

44 *Politis* 1930: 296-300; *Purković* 1999: 87-88.

45 *Politis* 1930: 301-302.

46 For a similar opinion, see: *Belyakova (Leber)* 2019: 23. It is also possible that the books were further used by a Slavonic (Serbian?) monastic or church community, as the manuscript *EBE* 2004 contains also translations of some Greek words into Old Church Slavonic - *Politis* 1991: 72; *Belyakova (Leber)* 2019: 22.

“my holy empress, pious augusta holy Elizabeth”⁴⁷ or “eternal memory to you, most pious augusta kyra Elizabeth, for the fact that my hands are busy with writing.”⁴⁸ These direct appellations suggest that the scribe expected his work to be read by the sponsor herself and that his lauds were to be appreciated and received by her; therefore, he most probably applied the official title befitted to his patroness. He also praised Jelena for features typical to a male ruler,⁴⁹ such as charity and wisdom: “my holy empress ruling augusta, source and root of charity, ornamented by all virtues and wisdom, and the fatherland of yours is the Heavenly metropolis.”⁵⁰ Finally, in the petition addressed to the Virgin, the scribe directly calls Jelena/Jelisaveta a “Roman ruler,” along with her son Stefan Uroš, and asks to “strengthen them.”⁵¹

Thus, looking at the independent patronage acts undertaken by *Tsaritsa* Jelena/Jelisaveta, one may suggest that they were the reflections of certain policy lines activated in course of her rule. Primarily, all acts of patronage show the importance of the two Churches (Greek and Serbian) for Jelena’s government. Their reconciliation was one of the main goals of her politics, and she was ready to use all the necessary artistic, memorial, and diplomatic means to achieve it. Her second point was the support of her ruling status by the Greek and Serbian ecclesiastic and monastic institutions in the region. By taking a closer look at the naming formulae used for Jelena/Jelisaveta by the scribes who produced the manuscripts, one may notice that the ruling formula or imperial title was combined with the monastic name, and, thus, the manuscripts promoted Jelena/Jelisaveta not simply as a pious ruler, but as a ruling nun. Third, the constant presence of the male names of her husband and son as reference points of her authority (in the donor composition of Matejčce, the Lavra donation charter, and the colophons) demonstrate that Jelena/Jelisaveta strove to acquire the pious memory of her deceased husband as a certain basis for the legitimacy of her own rule and that of her son’s.

47 Δέσποινά μου αγία εὐσεβέστατη αὐγούστα αγία Ἐλισάβετ - *Politis* 1930: 290.

48 Αἰωνία σου ἡ μνήμη εὐσεβέστατη αὐγούστα κυρά Ἐλισάβετ ὅτι ἐχόρτασαν αἱ χεῖρες μου γράψιμον - *Politis* 1930: 291.

49 *Hunger* 1964: 123-143, 240-243.

50 Δέσποινά μου αγία εὐσεβέστατη ἄννασσα αὐγούστα· πηγὴ (καὶ) ρίζα τῆς ἐλεημοσύνης· (καὶ) ἀρετὴ πάση (καὶ) σοφία κεκοσμημένη· εἰ γε πατρὶς μὲν σὴ ἢ ἄνω μητρόπολις - *Politis* 1930: 291.

51 Ἀλλ’ ὡ παρθένε κράτυνον τοὺς ἀνακτας Ῥωμαίους Στέφανον Οὐρσεῖν (καὶ) τ(ὴν) μ(ητέ) ρα τούτου ἀγί(αν) Ἐλισάβετ - *Politis* 1930: 291. Here, I prefer to translate the Greek ἄναξ as ‘ruler,’ in order to avoid the confusion of the terms ἄναξ and κράλης.

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Царица Елена (Елисавета) Сръбска като независим покровител на изкуствата между 1355 и 1366 г.

Анна Адашинская

Целта на статията е разглеждането на политиката, свързана с изкуствата, водена от царица Елена (Елисавета) Сръбска, като се проследява ролята ѝ на покровител в областта на архитектурата, декоративните изкуства и книжнината по време на самостоятелното ѝ управление в Серес (1355–1366). Анализирайки паметниците, които са свързани с нея или на които се приписва нейното спомоществователство, се стреми да покаже по какъв начин нейната ангажираност отразява основните политически насоки в управлението ѝ и по какъв начин личността ѝ оказва влияние върху формирането на нейната собствена управленска идеология.

Царица Елена (1315–1374), племенница на българския цар Иван Александър и съпруга на сръбския крал (цар) Стефан Душан, е добре позната в сръбската и международната историография поради активното ѝ участие в политическия живот на Балканите през Средновековието, а също така и необичайния факт, че тя посещава Света гора, който е забранен за жени. Тя е била деен покровител на манастири и изкуства не само като кралица/царица при управлението крал/цар Стефан Душан (1331–1355), но и като вдовица на краля и независим управник на Серската област между 1355 и 1366 г. През 1356 г. тя приема монашество под името Елисавета, но остава в двореца си и продължава да се занимава с политика.

За да разберем същността на политиките на Елена в областта на изкуствата, е нужно да те да бъдат разгледани в рамките на политическия климат от периода и да бъдат оценени във връзка със статута на Сръбското кралство и Църквата между 1355 и 1366 г. Статията разглежда първия акт на независимо покровителство от Елена за стенописи в манастира Матейче, датиращи от 1348–1352 г. и подчертава тясната връзка между царицата, като основател, и духовниците (патриарх Йонаникий и игумен Макарий), изобразени в близост до ктиторската композиция. Това е първата индикация за по-късните политики на Елена, когато, като вдовица, тя разчита на църковния йерей, подкрепящ владетелския статут на замонашената вдовица.

Следващите актове на покровителство трябва да бъдат поставени в рамките на църковния конфликт между Сръбската и Византийската църква, предизвикан от създаването на независимата Сръбска църква и империята на сърби и гърци от Стефан Душан през 1346 г. В резултат на тези събития константинополският патриарх Калист отлъчва сърбите и прекъсва връзките между две общности. По този начин щедрият дар на Елена за атонската Лавра от 1361 г. е обусловен от възпоменанието на покойния ѝ съпруг като благочестив човек и велик православен владетел, равен на другите императори. Това е първият ѝ опит да промени образа на миналите събития.

През 1363 г. владетелката се възползва от възможността да внесе хармония във взаимоотношенията между враждуващите църкви с поставяне началото на култ към патриарх Калист в Серес. Калист, който отлъчил сърбите, починал по време на мисията си в двора на Елена, а владетелката започва да го почита като свой защитник, построявайки параклис в близост до серската катедрала, за да приюти тялото на патриарха.

И най-накрая, дарението на няколко гръцки ръкописа за Атон показва съществуващата представа за Елена като властваща монахиня. Изобразена на всички места като суверен заедно със своя син, възхвалена от надписите за качества ѝ на владетел, използвайки съчетанието от нейната светска титла (августа, деспина) и монашеското ѝ име Елисавета.

Така че, можем да считаме, че покровителствените действия на Елена/Елисавета са отражение на нейното управление и идеология. Помиряването на църквите обаче е била нейната основна политическа цел, а след това и подкрепата на гръцките и сръбските църковни и монашески институции в региона. Не на последно място, ползвайки имената на своя син и това на покойния си съпруг, царицата създава законно основание за собственото си управление като техен наследник.